

THE CONCEPT OF LOYALTY IN THE POETRY OF ZULFIYA ISRAILOVA**Azamatova Sevinch Shukhrat qizi**

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Abstract. This article highlights the artistic interpretation of the concept of loyalty in Zulfiya's poetry. In the poet's work, feelings of love, loyalty, and human devotion are manifested as one of the main ideological directions of the lyrics. The article analyzes the symbolic and philosophical content of loyalty in Zulfiya's poetics, as well as its aspects related to the human spiritual world. As a result of the study, it is determined that loyalty in Zulfiya's poetry is interpreted not only as a personal feeling, but also as a high spiritual and moral value. In the poet's lyrics, loyalty is manifested as an important criterion of the human spiritual world and is expressed inextricably linked with love and life experiences.

Keywords: Zulfiya's lyrics, concept of loyalty, loyalty, love, lyrical hero, artistic interpretation.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается художественная интерпретация понятия верности в поэзии Зульфийи. В творчестве поэта чувства любви, верности и преданности проявляются как одно из главных идеологических направлений лирики. В статье анализируется символическое и философское содержание верности в поэтике Зульфийи, а также её аспекты, связанные с духовным миром человека. В результате исследования установлено, что верность в поэзии Зульфийи интерпретируется не только как личное чувство, но и как высокая духовно-нравственная ценность. В лирике поэта верность проявляется как важный критерий духовного мира человека и выражается неразрывно связанной с любовью и жизненным опытом.

Ключевые слова: лирика Зульфийи, понятие верности, верность, любовь, лирический герой, художественная интерпретация.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Zulfiya she'riyatida sadoqat konsepsiyasining badiiy talqini yoritiladi. Shoiri ijodida muhabbat, vafodorlik va insoniy sadoqat tuyg'ulari lirikaning asosiy g'oyaviy yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Maqolada Zulfiya poetikasida sadoqatning ramziy hamda falsafiy mazmuni, shuningdek, uning inson ruhiy olami bilan bog'liq jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijasida Zulfiya she'riyatida sadoqat nafaqat shaxsiy tuyg'u, balki yuksak ma'naviy-axloqiy qadriyat sifatida talqin etilishi aniqlanadi. Shoiri lirikasida vafodorlik inson ruhiy dunyosining muhim mezon sifatida namoyon bo'lib, muhabbat va hayotiy kechinmalar bilan uzviy bog'liq holda ifodalanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zulfiya lirikasi, sadoqat konsepsiyasi, vafodorlik, muhabbat, lirik qahramon, badiiy talqin.

INTRODUCTION

The work of the poetess Zulfiya, who created a delicate and touching image of human feelings, occupies a special place in Uzbek poetry. In her poems, universal human values such as love, loyalty, fidelity, humanity and goodness are expressed with high artistic skill. In particular, the motif of loyalty is one of the leading themes of the poet's lyrics, which is illuminated through various life experiences, spiritual suffering and complex states of the human soul. In Zulfiya's poetry, loyalty is interpreted not only as loyalty to love, but also as a person's loyalty to his own faith, memory and spiritual values.

The lyrical images and poetic images created by the poetess serve to deepen the understanding of the essence of loyalty. In her poems, this concept is manifested as a high virtue of the human psyche and is combined with sincere feelings. In this regard, studying the concept of loyalty in Zulfiya's work is not only of literary, but also of spiritual and educational importance.

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This article analyzes the artistic interpretation of loyalty in the poetess's poetry, its poetic means of expression, and its ideological and artistic characteristics.

METHODOLOGY

It is known that Zulfiya's poetry is distinguished by its sincere expression of feelings of love, loyalty and devotion. In the poet's life, Hamid Olimjon was not only her life partner, but also her source of creative inspiration and spiritual support. Therefore, in Zulfiya's lyrics, the feeling of love is combined with devotion. In the following lines, we can see the expression of the lyrical hero's boundless love and spiritual attachment to his beloved:

They say that when I see you,
A living fire burns in my eyes,
In the flames of that fire,
Forget everything else but you.

The "living fire" used in the verses expresses the power, ardor, and sincerity of love. The lyrical hero, describing the feelings that flare up in his heart when he sees his beloved, emphasizes that everything in the world becomes secondary to him. The line "Forget everything else but you" shows the high level of love. This line describes the attachment of the lover's entire being to a single person. The poet interprets love not as just a feeling, but as a high spiritual value that completely encompasses the spiritual world of a person and demands loyalty to him. For the lyrical hero, the beloved is so important that next to him all other things lose their value. The combination "except you" in the verse indicates that attention is focused on only one person. This is one of the important signs of loyalty. Because loyalty is manifested in a person's heart and soul being faithful to one person, not changing their feelings for him or her under the influence of time and circumstances. The fact that the lyrical hero's thoughts and imagination are occupied only with the person he or she loves shows his or her loyalty in love.

In the following excerpt from Zulfian Isroilova's poem "Spring has come, asking you questions", the motif of loyalty takes center stage, and the lyrical hero's loyalty to love and memory is depicted with great artistic skill:

In my heart, my words are in my hand,
I sing of life, I retreat.
You are in my dreams at night, in my memories during the day.
I am life, and you are life too.

These lines express the pain of separation in the heart of the lyrical hero and the desire to live despite it. The phrase "Hijroning qalbimda" in the first line means that the absence of the beloved person has left a deep mark on the heart. However, the phrase "sozing qo'limda" shows that the poet continues to create despite all the suffering. This is an expression of the spiritual strength and loyalty of a person.

The line "You are in my dreams at night, you are in my memory during the day" reveals the concept of loyalty even more deeply. The lyrical hero remembers his beloved not only during the day, but also accompanies him in his dreams. This is a vivid example of the stability of memory, spiritual connection and loyalty. For the poet, the beloved person is always with him spiritually, even if he is physically far away or not in life. The most touching part of the lines is the line "I am life, you are life too". Here the poet interprets loyalty at the highest level. The lyrical hero connects his life with the memory of his beloved. That is, as long as he lives, the name, memory and spiritual image of the beloved will continue to live. This is an artistic expression of not only love, but also lifelong loyalty. Thus, in these verses, loyalty is manifested by not forgetting the beloved, being faithful to his memory throughout his life, and preserving love in the heart despite the pain of separation. In Zulfiya's interpretation, loyalty is embodied as a high spiritual value that is not limited by time and distance, but lives in the human heart throughout his life.

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In addition, in Uzbek poetry, the name Zulfiya is revered as a singer of spring, love and loyalty. This definition is not without reason. The poetess's life and work are a bright example that can serve as an example for every Uzbek woman. In her works, the fate, dreams, aspirations and life experiences of an Uzbek woman occupy a particularly important place. Zulfiya sincerely and boldly expressed the joys and anxieties of women and girls in her poems. The poetess never tires of glorifying the tenderness, beauty and spiritual purity inherent in women. The image of nature is also important in Zulfiya's work. The poetess describes natural landscapes through colorful symbols and images, combining them with the feelings in the human heart. Her poems such as "Spring has come, questioning you", "My son, there will be no war", "Without you", "Heart" and "Poem" are popular among the people. After the death of the poetess's husband - the famous poet Hamid Olimjon, the poetess's feelings of longing and sorrow intensified. Despite this, she did not give up on the difficult trials of life. She continued to create with courage and became a bright symbol of devotion. Zulfiyakhanim not only engaged in creativity, but also raised her children and continued the literary work begun by Hamid Olimjon. The poetess expressed her boundless love for her life partner in many poems. In particular, her works such as "When the apricot blossoms", "Spring came, questioning you", "Did you see tears in my eyes?" and "I am looking" deeply reflect her devotion, love and suffering. Everyone who reads these poems feels the boundless love and longing in the poetess's heart. Despite the short life she spent with her husband, Zulfiya maintained her loyalty to her family and her husband for many years. Zulfiya is a great poetess who occupies a special place in Uzbek poetry. She is valued as a woman who embodies most of the human qualities. Her work was even more appreciated during the years of independence. In 2004, the Zulfiya State Prize was established in our country. This award is awarded to talented girls who have achieved high results in literature, art and other fields. Even today, Zulfiya's life and work serve as an example for many women. Her hard work, dedication, constant striving forward and creative pursuits arouse great admiration in the hearts of young people. The poetess' unique talent and exemplary life path remain an important spiritual heritage for today's generation.

CONCLUSION

Zulfiya's poetry is of particular importance in Uzbek literature as an artistic heritage that glorifies such high human values as love, loyalty and devotion. In the poetess's lyrics, the concept of loyalty is depicted in harmony with the spiritual perfection of a person, spiritual purity and boundless devotion to love. In her poems, loyalty is interpreted not only as loyalty to a loved one, but also as loyalty to memory, faith and human feelings.

The analyzed poetic lines show that in Zulfiya's poetics, loyalty found artistic expression through the spiritual experiences of the lyrical hero, the pain of exile and the immortality of love. In particular, in the poem "Spring came, questioning you", the idea of lifelong loyalty to the memory of a loved one, keeping him forever in the heart, occupies a leading place. The poetess interprets loyalty as a spiritual and moral value that transcends the boundaries of time and space. Thus, in Zulfiya's poetry, the concept of loyalty is inextricably linked with love and humanity, constituting one of the ideological and artistic foundations of her lyrical heritage. This shows that the poetess's work has not lost its relevance today and serves as an important source for educating the younger generation in the spirit of high spiritual qualities.

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